

An Investigation into the Relationship Among Depression, Maladaptive Behaviours and Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students, in North-Central, Nigeria

Ruth Ibukun Mcbrown, Prof. Yusuf Ahmadu, Dr. V.O. Adikwu

Department of Guidance and Counselling, University of Abuja

ruthmcbrown510@gmail.com

Abstract: *This study investigated the relationship among Depression, Maladaptive Behaviours and Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students, in North-central, Nigeria. The designs adopted for this study are descriptive survey and Ex - post- facto design. The population of this study comprised of Senior Secondary School year one (SSS I) in all public schools, in North-central, Nigeria. A sample size of 333 male and female SSS one respondents was used in this survey. A multi-stage sampling technique divides large population into stages to make the sampling process more practical. The reliability of the instrument was determined by a pilot test which was conducted using 40 respondents from Government Secondary School, Gwagwalada, in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja who did not participate in the main study. The test-retest method of reliability was used to obtain the data from the conducted pilot test to determine the reliability of the instrument. The data collected was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The study concluded that there significant relationship between depression and maladaptive behaviour of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria. The study also established that there is significant relationship between depression and the academic achievement of senior secondary school students. The study showed that there is significant relationship between depression and the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommends that more effort should be made by all the stakeholders in education especially parents, teachers and school counsellors to guide these students and help them to concentrate as well as participate fully in class activities, in order to address the issue of depression among the students in secondary schools.*

Keywords: *Academic Achievement, Depression, Maladaptive Behaviours.*

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1.0 Introduction

There are issues of social-economic pressure such as high cost of living which has continue to skyrocket on daily basis, high rate of unemployment, the cashless policy which is biting harder from all angles, conflicts as well as pressures from the academic environment that students go through on a daily basis. This to a large extent could affect the behaviour of students. Evans (2002) observed that students growing under the condition of economic hardship are at increased risk of behavioural problems, decrease in social competence and lower cognitive abilities.

This situation has created a link among depression, maladaptive behaviours and academic achievement of students in secondary school. Depression may affect students socially, emotionally and other facets of life thereby making them to perform below standard academically. Ohila (2014) opined that some students can go as far as indulging in lifestyles that they see as dangerous and ungodly, indulging in vices such as shoplifting, smoking, alcohol intake, gang rape, cultism e.t.c, and is often characterized by persistent sadness and loss of interest in activities that were usually being enjoyed, and also accompanied by the inability to carry out daily tasks, for at least a period of two weeks (WHO, 2014; WHO, 2017).

Depression is a worrisome issue which is rapidly spreading across countries, communities and individuals both young and old as well as adolescents, are not being exempted from this plague which is constantly on the increase. The researcher has personally observed that secondary school students are constantly undergoing different stages of development which can either make or mar their development with regards to their maturity, socialization process and independence. Those who have positive and encouraging adjustment to life problems often tend to escape symptoms of depression and maladaptive behaviour but those who go through negative socialization and poor adjustment to life problems are more inclined to go through depression (Mihalyi, 2022). Students begin to separate from their parents but still lack a clearly defined role in the society. It is often viewed as an emotionally intense and stressful stage of life (Mihalyi, 2022). Depression, which is one of the recent forms of emotional challenges that some students undergo, is often portrayed by feelings of sadness, anxiety, fear, guilt, anger, contempt and confused thinking (Peterson, Compass, Brooks-Gunn, Stemmler, Ey, & Grant, 1993). The term depression describes a wide range of emotional lows, from mere sadness to a pathological suicidal state (Nair, Paul, & John, 2004). Depression is a common mental problem often encountered in daily stress-filled life.

Maladaptive behaviour is the behaviour being displayed by students in an environment of learning that disregards both written and unwritten social norms as well as laid down rules of the school. It involves a wide variety of behaviours, such as outright delinquency to far more subtle forms of disruptive or antisocial behaviour. In addition, maladaptive behavior can be aimed at specific people (e.g., supervisors, teachers, individuals or peers), or more generalized, targeting anyone and anything. Such, behaviour can be an isolated event or periodic (Koerhuis & Oostdam 2014). Maladaptive behaviour is that which does not correspond to the accepted rules of a group of individuals or the society at large.

Academic achievement is being described as academic outcomes that show the extent to which a student has achieved his/her learning goals. It may refer to completion of educational benchmarks such as secondary school certificate (e.g WAEC) Academic achievement is often measured through examinations or continuous assessments (Tophat, 2022). Academic achievement is said to be the extent to which a student has attained his/her short or long term educational goals (Mohammed, 2010). Academic achievement is of great importance due to the fact that it is associated with positive outcomes. It is often believed that students who are academically successful with high level of socio-emotional intelligence are more likely to be employed and as well, have stable employment than those with less education (Regier, 2011).

The relationship among depression, maladaptive behaviours and academic achievement of students has become a major concern to counsellors, secondary school teachers and other stakeholders in the education system. It seems to be a complex problem when one attempts to understand the relationship among depression, maladaptive behaviours and academic achievement which appears like a tripod stand. Depression, maladaptive behaviours and academic achievement among secondary school students stand as a major concern to the society. Some students no longer take their education to be important but rather, they are known for showcasing different maladaptive behaviours such as bullying, truancy, lateness to school and others (Parker, 2014).

When students display symptoms of depression and maladaptive behaviours such as low self-esteem as well as difficulty in concentration in carrying out any activities, withdrawal from friends and family members, putting little efforts into school activities, constant lateness to school amongst others, these may interfere with the student's academics. The researcher has personally observed that poor academic achievement by secondary school students especially in the North-central region of the country may be related to depression as well as maladaptive behaviours. The school is a major and important environment where students grow and develop during the formative years (Peltzer, Pengpid, Olowu, & Olasupo 2013). In some of the secondary schools in the country especially those in the North-central, the environment of learning usually does not encourage nor facilitate the transfer of knowledge and probably as a result of this, students may not be motivated to put in their best in the area of academics but rather resort to maladaptive behaviours such as noise making, bullying, disobedience to constituted authority and a host of others. The researcher is of the opinion that both male and female secondary school students often involve in maladaptive behaviours as a way of expressing themselves (Patel, Araya, & Bolton, 2004).

This study focused on the relationship among depression, maladaptive behaviours and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria. The researcher believes that depression and maladaptive behaviour play key roles in the academic achievement of secondary school students. It is the lack of clarity that demands for this current research. It is the belief of this researcher that students in secondary schools are nation builders and leaders of tomorrow. Hence, if these elements are properly investigated, appropriate remediation programmes can be planned and executed to address the issue of depression and maladaptive behaviours and how it affects academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.

1.2 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the relationship among Depression, Maladaptive Behaviours and Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students, in North-central, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. determine the depressive behaviours of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.
- ii. find out the maladaptive behaviours of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.
- iii. determine the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.

1.3 Research Questions

The following research questions were addressed;

- 1) What are the depressive behaviours of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria?
- 2) What are the maladaptive behaviours of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria?
- 3) What is the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria?

1.4 Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between depression and maladaptive behaviours of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between depression and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between maladaptive behaviours and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.

2.0 Method

The designs adopted for this study are descriptive survey and Ex - post- facto design. Nworgu (1991) reported that a survey research is one in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group. The population of this study comprised of Senior Secondary School year one (SSS I) in all public schools, in North-central, Nigeria. This includes: Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, Plateau and Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The overall figure of the population is 181,769 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2021). A sample size of 333 male and female SSS one respondents was used in this survey. The sample size was determined based on recommendation by Glenn (2012). That 10- 20% of a population should be considered as sample of a given population which is 20% of the sample schools' population in public secondary schools in North-central, Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique divides large population into stages to make the sampling process more practical. At stage one, simple random sampling technique of (Dip-hat method) was used. The instruments for this study are three, a checklist, questionnaire and Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) result. The questionnaire tagged "Relationship among Depression, Maladaptive Behaviours and Academic Achievement Questionnaire (RADMBAAQ)", was used as the survey instrument to collect the information needed for the study. The questionnaire was structured along a four-point scale by the researcher which consisted of two sections; A and B. Section A was designed to elicit information on the demographic data of the respondents, which include; School, State, gender and location. Section B was used to elicit information on Relationship among Depression, Maladaptive Behaviours and Academic Achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria. The instrument contained 47 items in all. The validity of the instrument was ascertained by the researchers' supervisors and two other lecturers in the Faculty of Education, University of Abuja for the purpose of face content and construct validity. They studied the items and assessed the suitability of the language, the adequacy and relevance of the items in addressing the research questions and hypotheses bearing in mind the purpose of the study. Their corrections and comments were used to modify the questionnaire. The corrected version of the questionnaire was approved by the researcher's Supervisors. The reliability of the instrument was determined by a pilot test which was conducted using 40 respondents from Government Secondary School, Gwagwalada, in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja who did not participate in the main study. The test-retest method of reliability was used to obtain the data from the conducted pilot test to determine the reliability of the instrument. The data collected was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics include: percentage, frequency counts, standard deviation and mean scores for the demographic data and research questions. The decision rule was 2.50. Any score from 2.50 and above was considered agreed and any score below 2.50 was considered disagreed. The inferential statistics used includes Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC), t-test and multiple regression for the hypotheses. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Hypothesis more than 0.05 will be accepted while hypothesis less than 0.05 will be rejected. Hypotheses 1-3 were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, hypotheses 4-9 were tested using t-test and hypothesis 10 was tested using multiple regression.

3.0 Data Analysis and Results

Answering to Research Questions

This section contains data on the research questions raised to guide this study.

Research Question One: What are the depressive behaviours of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean scores and Standard Deviation of respondents' take on depressive behaviours of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.

N=333

S/no	Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
6.	I feel sad always.	164	139	27	3	3.39	0.839	Agreed
7.	I hate myself sometimes.	19	69	128	117	1.97	0.681	Disagreed
8.	I sometimes exhibit conditions that affect my mood, thinking and behaviour	137	164	28	4	3.30	0.834	Agreed
9.	I usually have sleeping difficulties and feelings of irritation	174	139	19	1	3.46	0.843	Agreed
10.	I find it difficult to concentrate or participate fully in class activities	202	126	4	1	3.59	0.855	Agreed
11.	I occasionally take drugs to calm my nerves.	104	116	83	30	2.88	0.779	Agreed
12.	I sometimes consume alcohol	101	116	89	27	2.87	0.787	Agreed
13.	I have symptoms of depression in my family.	91	155	49	38	2.90	0.753	Agreed
14.	I prefer to be alone rather than with people.	61	167	47	58	2.69	0.742	Agreed
15.	I have been eating more than usual and have noticed changes	140	177	14	2	3.37	0.781	Agreed

	in my weight.									
16.	I am easily fatigued.	63	165	60	45	2.74	0.762	Agreed		
17.	I feel emotionally stressed.	86	163	68	16	2.96	0.753	Agreed		
18.	I perform poorly in my academics.	108	151	59	15	3.06	0.785	Agreed		
19.	My parents frequently have intense and unresolved conflicts	89	167	59	18	2.98	0.788	Agreed		
20.	I usually bully some students in school.	80	177	48	28	2.93	0.781	Agreed		
21.	I feel I have psychological as well as physical health challenges.	106 183 36 8				3.16	0.818	Agreed	0.851	Agreed
22.	I experience hormonal changes which often affect my mood.	67 171 68 27				2.83	0.768	Agreed		
23.	I sometimes have fear of intimidation, coercion, and ridiculing when amongst people.	79 168 70 16				2.93	0.769	Agreed		
24	I fidget most times and find it difficult to relax on my own.	56 149 93 35				2.68	0.748	Agreed		
25.	I get angry easily and find it hard to control my temper.	65 169 66 33				2.80	0.765	Agreed		
26	It seems I have a history of mental illness in my family.	54 153 96 30				2.69	0.745	Agreed		
	Sectional Mean					2.96	0.780	Agreed		

Table 1 with the overall mean score of 2.96 presented the depressive behaviours of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria. From the analysis, it was discovered that over average of

the respondents agreed to all the items in the table as some of the major depressive behaviours of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria. Based on the above, the researcher concluded that all the items in table 1 except item two were the major depressive behaviours of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria which is in line with the decision rule that 2.50 and above be agreed and below be disagreed.

Research Question Two: What are the maladaptive behaviours of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean scores and Standard Deviation of respondents' take on maladaptive behaviours of secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.

N=333

S/no	Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
27.	I destroyed school properties at one time or the other.	115	167	41	10	3.16	0.801	Agreed
28.	I do not care about other people's feelings.	126	177	26	4	3.28	0.826	Agreed
29.	I dislike social contact.	135	163	28	7	3.28	0.826	Agreed
30.	I perform poorly in my academics.	165	152	12	4	3.44	0.833	Agreed
31.	I often skip classes.	107	163	52	11	3.10	0.797	Agreed
32.	I am easily overwhelmed by feelings of negativity.	78	125	93	37	2.73	0.743	Agreed
33.	I find it difficult to interact with other people apart from my parents.	64	164	79	26	2.80	0.778	Agreed
34.	I disobey school rules and regulations.	167	140	24	2	3.42	0.831	Agreed
35.	I feel my environment has great influence on me.	100	177	46	10	3.10	0.797	Agreed
36.	I do not want to indulge in physical exercise regularly.	61	136	91	45	2.64	0.731	Agreed
37.	I feel my parents do not give me preferential treatment.	67	159	79	28	2.80	0.778	Agreed
38.	I find it difficult to participate fully in activities.	70	182	64	17	2.91	0.786	Agreed
39.	I do not behave myself when interacting with others.	88	188	49	8	3.10	0.797	Agreed
40.	I feel my parents do not guide me in my academics.	73	190	44	26	2.93	0.788	Agreed
41.	I indulge in immoral acts occasionally.	78	184	48	23	2.95	0.789	Agreed
42.	I feel I am affected by my parents' constant argument.	64	126	94	49	2.61	0.730	Agreed
43.	I feel my parents do not shower their love on me.	66	138	88	41	2.68	0.742	Agreed
44	I hate to belong to a social support group	165	125	25	18	3.31	0.832	Agreed

45	I feel my parents and teachers do not pamper me.	116	188	20	9	3.23	0.822	Agreed
46	I feel I can easily manipulate others to my advantage.	89	131	75	38	2.81	0.779	Agreed
47	I hate wearing the correct uniform to school	116	173	29	15	3.17	0.818	Agreed
Sectional Mean						3.02	0.792	Agreed

Table 2 with the sectional mean score of 3.02 presented the maladaptive behaviours of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria. From the analysis, it was discovered that, over average of the respondents agreed to all the items as some of the major maladaptive behaviours of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.

Based on the above, the researcher concluded that all the items in the table were the major maladaptive behaviours of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria which is in line with the decision rule that 2.50 and above be agreed and below be disagreed.

Research Question Three: What is the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean Score and Standard Deviation of Respondents' academic achievement in Senior Secondary School Students

S/no	Subjects	N	\bar{X}	SD
1.	English Language	333	2.42	0.34
2.	Mathematics	333	2.45	0.45
3.	Social Studies	333	2.43	0.43
4.	Basic Science	333	2.46	0.49
Sectional Mean			2.44	0.43

Table 3 with the sectional mean score of 2.44 was structured to find out the academic achievement of students in Mathematics, English Language, Social Studies and Basic Science. The analysis shows that students have a mean score of 2.42 in English Language, 2.45 in Mathematics, 2.43 in Social Studies and 2.46 in Basic Science. This indicated that, students' performance is below average.

3.1 Testing of Hypotheses

The null hypotheses were tested using PPMC, t-test and multiple regression statistics. All tests were conducted at $P > 0.05$ level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between Depression and maladaptive behaviour of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.

Table 4: PPMCC result on the difference between depression and maladaptive behaviours of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.

Variable	N	X	SD	df	r-cal Value	r-crit	Level of Sig. (P)	Decision
Depression	331	2.96	0.754	2	0.135	0.185	0.043	significant
Maladaptive Behaviour		3.02	0.758					

*=significant at 0.05 level ($p < 0.05$)

Table 4 shows the significant relationship between depression and maladaptive behaviour of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria. The *r*-value of 0.135 indicates a positive relationship. The probability value (*p*-value) is 0.043 which is less than 0.05, the hypothesis is therefore rejected and was concluded that there is a significant relationship between depression and maladaptive behaviour of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between depression and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.

Table 5: PPMCC Test result of relationship between depression and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.

Variable	N	X	SD	df	r-cal Value	r-crit	Level of Sig.	Decision
Depression	331	2.96	0.75	2	0.235	0.185	0.041	significant
Academic Achievement		2.44	0.43					

***=significant at 0.05 level (p<0.05)**

Table 5 shows the significant relationship between depression and the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria. The *r*-calculated value of 0.235 was greater than the *r*-critical value of 0.185. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This showed that there is a significant relationship between depression and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between maladaptive behaviour and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.

Table 6: PPMCC Test result of relationship between Maladaptive and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.

Variable	N	X	SD	df	r-cal Value	r-crit	Level of Sig.	Decision
Maladaptive	331	3.02	0.758	2	0.235	0.185	0.041	significant
Academic Achievement		2.44	0.43					

***=significant at 0.05 level (p<0.05)**

Table 6 shows the significant relationship between depression and the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria. The *r*-calculated value of 0.235 was greater than the *r*-critical value of 0.185. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This showed that there is a significant relationship between depression and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central Nigeria.

3.3 Summary of Findings

The following are major findings of the study. The findings of the study revealed that:

1. mood disorder that changes how students think, feelings of irritation, sleeping difficulties as shown by students in schools as well as having difficulty in concentrating or participating fully in class activities amongst others are some of the depressive behaviours manifested by students in senior secondary schools in North-central, Nigeria.

2. having no regard for ethical rules and right of others as seen in school, behaviours that does not conform to societal expectation which is usually popular among students, vandalism, bullying and truancy amongst others are some of the maladaptive behaviours expressed by senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.

3. academic achievement of students in Mathematics, English Language, Social Studies and Basic Science of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria is below average. This could be attributed to depression and maladaptive behaviours being manifested in schools.

3.4 Discussion of Findings

The result of the study revealed that mood disorder that changes how students think, feelings of irritation and sleeping difficulties shown by students in schools, difficulties to concentrate or participate fully in class activities amongst others are some of the depressive behaviours shown by students in senior secondary schools in North-central, Nigeria. This is supported by Animba and Obika (2020) who asserted that depressive behaviours is different from usual mood fluctuations and short-lived emotional responses to everyday life challenges but has a long lasting with moderate or severe intensity to disrupt normal life, thereby affecting an individual's ability to function at work, school, and society. Depression is classified as a mood disorder. It is described as feelings of sadness, loss or anger that interferes with a person's everyday activities (APA, 2013).

Bruce (2021) equally emphasized that student depression tends to come and go in episodes. Once a student undergoes a bout of depression, such is likely to get depressed again at some point. The consequence of letting depression go untreated can be extremely serious and even deadly. The findings of the study disclosed that having no regard for ethical rules and right of others, behaviours that does not conform to societal expectation, vandalism, bullying and truancy amongst others are some of the maladaptive behaviours of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria. The various forms of student maladaptive behaviours are late coming, drug and alcoholic abuse, bullying, love affairs, vandalism, assault on the school prefects, insult on educators, wearing the wrong school uniform, negative use of the mobile phone, smoking, writing or using foul language in class, work not done, class disruption and immoral acts (Gutuza & Mapolisa, 2015; Jeeroburkhan, 2016).

Maladaptive behaviour is said to be as undesirable by the norms of conventional society and the institutions of adult authority, and its occurrence usually elicits some kinds of social control response (Aboh, Nwankwo, Agu, & Chikwendu, 2014).

The result of the study further indicated that the academic achievement of students in Mathematics, English studies, Social Studies and Basic Science of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria, is below average. This could be attributed to depression and maladaptive behaviours. This is in line with Goodwin (2020) who emphasized that depression is said to be one of the top five impediments to academic performance. The number of students being diagnosed with depression is on the increase and is also among the major obstruction to academic achievement. Better help (2023) also corroborated that maladaptive behaviours serves as coping mechanisms in students and such behaviours may lead to isolation, relationship issues as well as negative consequences on academics. Fareo (2019) posited that students' unruly behaviour has constantly affected school academic achievement to the extent that teachers are unable to cover the contents of the school curriculum and this often result in the production of half-baked graduates.

3.5 Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concluded that there significant relationship between depression and maladaptive behaviour of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria. The study also established that there is significant relationship between depression and the academic achievement of senior

secondary school students. The study showed that there is significant relationship between depression and the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria.

The following recommendations were made based on results of findings:

1. That more effort should be made by all the stakeholders in education especially parents, teachers and school counsellors to guide these students and help them to concentrate as well as participate fully in class activities, in order to address the issue of depression among the students in secondary schools.
2. That parents and other stakeholders in education should do more to inculcate the right attitude and values in the life of the students in order to bring the issues of maladaptive behaviours amongst senior secondary school students in North-central, Nigeria, to the barest minimum if not eradicated.
3. More effort should be made by the school counsellors by creating awareness and sensitization on the effects of depression and maladaptive behaviours on students' academic achievement.

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